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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ESG STRATEGY IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

Khusenova Mekhrangiz Gayratovna

WIUT, PhD candidate,

“Silk Road” IUTCH, Tourism department, assistant-teacher

Abstract: The hotel industry, a significant contributor to global tourism revenue, has shown steady growth, with Uzbekistan experiencing rapid development in its hotel sector, particularly in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Bukhara. This article discusses the global trends in sustainable tourism and the integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices, highlighting their alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Gives recommendations to implement ESG strategy in Uzbekistan.

Key words: hotel industry, ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), waste management, energy efficiency.

Annotatsiya: Mehmonxona sanoati global turizm daromadlariga katta hissa qo'shuvchi muhim soha bo'lib, barqaror o'sishni namoyon etmoqda. O'zbekistonda mehmonxona sektori, ayniqsa Toshkent, Samarqand va Buxoro shaharlarida jadal rivojlanish kuzatilmoqda. Ushbu maqola barqaror turizmning global tendensiyalari va atrof-muhit, ijtimoiy va boshqaruv (ESG) amaliyotlarining integratsiyasini muhokama qiladi, ularning Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining Barqaror Rivojlanish Maqsadlari (SDGs) bilan mosligini ta'kidlaydi. O'zbekistonda ESG strategiyasini amalga oshirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mehmonxona sanoati, ESG (Atrof-muhit, ijtimoiy va boshqaruv), Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlari (SDGs), chiqindilarni boshqarish, energiya samaradorligi.

Аннотация: Гостиничная индустрия, вносящая значительный вклад в глобальные доходы от туризма, демонстрирует устойчивый рост. В Узбекистане наблюдается быстрое развитие гостиничного сектора, особенно в Ташкенте, Самарканде и Бухаре. В данной статье рассматриваются глобальные тенденции в устойчивом туризме и интеграция экологических, социальных и управленческих (ESG) практик, подчеркивается их соответствие Целям устойчивого развития (ЦУР) Организации Объединенных Наций. Даны рекомендации по внедрению ESG-стратегии в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: гостиничная индустрия, ESG (Экология, социальная сфера и управление), Цели устойчивого развития (ЦУР), Управление отходами, Энергоэффективность.

INTRODUCTION

The hotel industry is considered one of the dominant services in tourism sphere since it consists 50 – 60 % of revenue of the tourism industry. According to UNWTO, tourism services including accommodation, food and drink, entertainment, shopping and other services and goods have generated record income USD 1.9 trillion in 2024, this is about 3% higher than before the pandemic, USD 1.481 billion in 2019[1]. In the last few years, hotel Industry of Uzbekistan is also developing rapidly specifically, number of hotels and rooms are increased noticeably, especially in Tashkent, Samarkand and Bukhara.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In 2018, total number of hotels in Uzbekistan was 916 in 2018 and it reached to 1 387 in 2023; this number continuous to grow up[2]. The largest number of hotels – 210, 160 and 125 - are located in Tashkent, Samarkand and Bukhara respectively in 2023 (Figure 1). Tashkent consistently shows the highest occupancy rates, reaching 88% in 2023, indicating strong demand. Samarkand sees steady increases, almost 80% in 2023, reflecting its importance as a cultural tourism hub. Regions like Khiva and Andijan, starting with lower occupancy rates, show gradual improvement, suggesting growing tourist interest (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Growth of hotel numbers in Uzbekistan by regions (2018-2023)*

Figure 2a. Hotel Occupancy rates by regions (2018-2023)*

Figure 2b. Growth of hotel Capacity (2018-2023)*

*By author according to Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan

The research views and development indicators in many industries as well as in hotel industry have been changed since the world has faced many natural, environmental and social problems. Huge flow of international tourists around the world has directly and indirectly impact on environment, society and nature through transport, hotels, accommodations, food services and other thousands of hospitality facilities and services. In 2015, UN General Assembly adopted 17 Sustainable Development Goals towards 2030 that aimed to make the world better place to live [3]. Tourism and hospitality industry can make affordable contribution to achieve:

Goal 8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.

Target 8.9 By 2030, devise and implement policies to promote sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products

Goal 12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.

Target 12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources

Target 12.3 By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer level and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses.

Target 12.5 By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse
Target 12.6 Encourage companies, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle.

Target 12.b Develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable development impacts for sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products.

ESG transformation in tourism sphere especially in the hotel industry also directly and indirectly contribute to achieve other SDGs like Gender equality, efficient Water use, affordable and clean energy, climate action, sustainable cities and communities and partnerships for the goals.

UNWTO with collaboration with the University of Oxford (Oxford SDG Impact Lab) have been developing the project “ESG framework for tourism businesses” [4]. The aim of the project to create standardized ESG metrics that are measurable unlike CSR and SDGs including greenhouse gas emissions, waste and water management, employee well-being, gender equality community engagement, rights of shareholder and others. The project is covering main Environmental, Social and Governance factors (table 1).

Table 1. ESG factors.

Environmental	Social	Governance
Tackling challenges related to climate change and minimizing carbon emissions. Ensuring the protection and sustainability of biodiversity. Adopting measures to optimize water usage and cons Implementing effective waste reduction and recycling programs. Enhancing energy efficiency and monitoring consumption levels. Improving air quality standards through targeted initiatives. Promoting responsible land management to reduce environmental harm. Encouraging employee freedom of association in the workplace. Preventing and eliminating child labor practices. Addressing issues of forced or involuntary labor. Prioritizing health and safety for all employees. Promoting equal opportunities, diversity, and non-discrimination in hiring and operations.		Meeting compliance and reporting obligations with clear frameworks. Strengthening risk management strategies across operations. Establishing and adhering to ethical codes of conduct and principles. Ensuring transparency and regular disclosure of business practices. Developing anti-corruption initiatives to maintain organizational integrity. Protecting and upholding the rights of shareholders.

In modern context ESG concept initially has been introduced in 2004 in The Global Compact report that recommended to incorporate ESG factors in business to achieve sustainable development, increase investment level and have positive social and environmental impact [5]. ESG stands for environmental, Social and Governance factors to assess metrics of non-financial factors. The three pillars of ESG represent a framework of criteria that company leaders and stakeholders use to evaluate a business's long-term effects on the environment and society[6]. Environmental factors measure how company impact on environment and natural resources along with climate change. Social factors measure how company impact on social aspects including its employees and the society (local people). Governance factors consider company's operations management and leadership positions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article methods of analysis, synthesis, and statistical analysis are used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The core of ESG principles came from CSR standards that began in the 1950s [7]. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has focus on non-financial aspect of a company which consider society, nature, environment and governance. The visualisation of ESG evolution (Figure 3) has been developed by Passas (2024) [8]

started with Emergence of ESG in 2000s that introduced standardized metrics like GRO, PRI and regulatory alignment. Mainstreaming of ESG had occurred in 2010s that became investor-driven, SDG alignment and integration into decision-making process. Lastly, in 2020s, ESG has been integrating into strategy proactively, impacts are measurable and focusing on innovation (figure 3).

Figure 3. the evolution of ESG.

According to Polbennikov et al. (2016) [9], ESG ratings positively influence a company’s financial performance. Companies that emphasize ESG demonstrate stronger engagement, possess greater competitive advantages, maintain healthier financial positions, and exhibit more effective leadership compared to those that do not (S&P Global, 2020) [10]. Also, they can achieve improved marketing outcomes, including the establishment and reinforcement of strong brand identities (Lin et al., 2024) [11]. Hotels implemented ESG measures have been found more resilient during the crisis time namely COVID-19 pandemic [12]. Global hotel chains namely Hilton, Marriot are actively implementing and promoting ESG measurements in their management system. Hilton and its sub brand hotels annually give their ESG report in details, how they implemented measures and what results they got. In 2018, Hilton adopted “Travel with purpose 2030 goals” which align with SDGs to achieve ESG goals [13]. Namely:

Environmental goals:

- Reduce direct emissions intensity by 75% by 2030.
- Cut emissions from franchised properties by 56% by 2030.
- Move towards achieving a net-zero carbon future.
- Decrease water usage intensity by 50% by 2030.
- Lower waste sent to landfills by 50% by 2030.

Social goals

- Offer 5 million learning and career growth opportunities by 2030, prioritizing underrepresented groups.
- Achieve 50% gender diversity in leadership roles globally by 2027.
- Reach 25% ethnic diversity in U.S. leadership positions by 2027.
- Positively influence 20 million community members by 2030 through local aid, disaster relief, and economic initiatives.
- Promote responsible practices throughout 100% of supply chain operations.

Governance goals:

- Support public policies aligned with sustainability and community-focused objectives.
- Partner with cross-industry networks to advance sustainability goals.
- Maintain governance through advanced tools (e.g., LightStay) and robust oversight systems. In 2023, Hilton hotels launched Hilton LightStay platform to analyse and monitor Environmental, Social and Governance measurements.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

ESG implementation in Uzbekistan is on earlier stage, a lot of methodologies and theories have been created by Uzbek scientists according to Sustainable practices in tourism and hospitality industries and eco hotels. In order to implement ESG strategy first we need to analyse the current ESG practise like energy use,

water consumption, waste management, social and governance policies – Conduct a Baseline Assessment. International standards (UN's SDGs or GSTC standards) and frameworks should compare and give adopted methodology for hotels in Uzbekistan. Next, ESG strategy should be developed: setting clear goals, aligning with national policy. To implement ESG strategy hotel need to adopt green technologies like energy-efficient appliances, solar panels, water-saving technologies. In addition, need to promote recycling programs. For social actions need to: Launch training programs on ESG principles for employees; Promote cultural tourism and collaborate with local communities; Implement policies for diversity and inclusion. For Governance Practices need to: Introduce regular sustainability reporting; Use digital tools to track and manage ESG metrics (e.g., energy consumption tracking systems).

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